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Indra Martian Permana, Fadzli Adam

Islamic State of Iraq and Syria (ISIS)
Terrorism Action in Indonesia Between
2014-2018

Marhamah

Reform of The Islamic Education System
in Indonesia According to
Azyumardi Azra

**Mohammad Normaaruf Abd Hamid,
Anas Mohd Yunus**

Application of The Concept of Hifz Al-Din
in Shariah Compliant Business
Management

**Sufian Awae, Nur Salina Binti Ismail,
Mohammad Halabieh**

Listening Comprehension Orientations
and Strategies in Learning English
Language

**AbdulFattah AbdulGaniyy, Ibraheem
Alani AbdulKareem**

Islamic Banking and Global Financial
Crises: A Review of Liquidity Risk
Management

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MAY 2020

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THE EFFECTIVENESS OF DA'WAH APPROACH THROUGH MULTIMEDIA AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS ALUMNI OF IBRAHIMY UNIVERSITY, INDONESIA

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Abstract

Today we have been living with multimedia, something that we can not ignore. Even, most of us can not live without it. Multimedia have changed many things in our lives. We can listen to the music, view pictures, and watch videos from various platforms. Despite offering so many facilities, multimedia can be very dangerous for college students in the booming of social media and social chat. College students alumni in East Java prefer to enjoy multimedia through Facebook platform rather than another conventional platform. Therefore, da'wah in the present of time has a very big challenge among college students. Without the right approach, da'wah by utilizing multimedia has no significant impact. This research is a quantitative research that tests the effectiveness of da'wah approach through text, image, and video and through facebook platform as a mediator among college students alumni. The purpose of this research is to know the effectiveness of da'wah approach that college students alumni are interested in. The population of this research is college students alumni who use facebook located in the province of East Java, Indonesia. Respondents of this research amounted to 100 people as samples taken from alumnus of Ibrahimy University. Questionnaires are used as data collection methods. Data analysis method used is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) using IBM SPSS Amos software. The result of this research show that facebook platform has a significant impact on college students alumni interest

in da'wah approach through multimedia. It's mean video, picture, and text had a significant effect on Facebook platform. The results of this research can be used as a reference by the Islamic practitioners both individual and institutional who want to make da'wah through multimedia have positive impact.

Keywords: *Islam, Da'wah Approach, Cyber Da'wah, Multimedia, Students*

Introduction

Da'wah means calling activities and convincing others to accept certain beliefs. Barghuts (1995) define da'wah as: "systematic and structured hard work aimed to introduce the essence of Islam to all human beings". Syaikh Ali Mahfudz (1979: 17) define da'wah with the terms below :

حِثُّ النَّاسِ عَلَى الْخَيْرِ وَالْهُدَى وَالْإِرْشَادَاتِ وَالْأَمْرُ بِالْمَعْرُوفِ
وَالْتَّهْيِ عَنِ الْمُنْكَرِ لِيَفُوزُوا بِسَعَادَةِ الْعَاجِلِ وَالْآجِلِ

The effort to bring mankind to do a good thing, to follow the guidance, to instruct them for "amar ma'ruf nahi munkar" so that they can achieve happiness in this world and hereafter.

Shihab, (1992) defines da'wah as a call of faithfulness to turn a bad state into a better and perfect state for our self and society. While Omar, (2004) defines da'wah is an attempt to invite people in ways wise to the true path in accordance with the command of God for the goodness in the world and the hereafter. Other Muslim scholars, Sulthon (2003) explained that da'wah is

a process attempts to persuade others to believe in Allah SWT. Believers in the sense of obeying his command and abandoning his ban. Including believing in Prophets, believing in Angels, believing in the Quran, believing in the day of judgment and believes that good and bad provisions come from Allah SWT.

Syaikh Abdullah Barjas Alu Abdil Karim (2012) explains that if Allah gives to a Muslim a science and a deed (i'Imu & a'mal), then he should immediately convey the goodness through the da'wah method, by inviting humans to return to the way of Allah with a real proposition (*hujjah*) based on evidence of the greatness of Allah SWT. Because this is the work of Prophet Muhammad SAW. Allah SWT said:

قُلْ هَذِهِ سَبِيلِي أَدْعُو إِلَى اللَّهِ عَلَى بَصِيرَةٍ أَنَا وَمَنِ اتَّبَعَنِي وَسُبْحَانَ اللَّهِ وَمَا أَنَا مِنَ الْمُشْرِكِينَ ﴿١٧٨﴾

Say: This is my way: I call to Allah, I and those who follow me being certain, and glory be to Allah, and I am not one of the polytheists. (Surah Yusuf 12:108)

He also said that Allah SWT will elevate the degree of people who call to Allah ways compared to other classes. Allah SWT said:

وَمَنْ أَحْسَنُ قَوْلًا مِّمَّن دَعَا إِلَى اللَّهِ وَعَمِلَ صَالِحًا وَقَالَ إِنَّنِي مِنَ الْمُسْلِمِينَ ﴿٣٣﴾

And who speaks better than he who calls to Allah while he himself does good, and says: I am surely of those who submit? (Surah Fussilat 41:33)

Da'wah is a duty for every Muslim. The command to do

da'wah has been described in many of Allah's words. Allah SWT said:

كُنْتُمْ خَيْرَ أُمَّةٍ أُخْرِجَتْ لِلنَّاسِ تَأْمُرُونَ بِالْمَعْرُوفِ وَتَنْهَوْنَ عَنِ الْمُنْكَرِ وَتُؤْمِنُونَ بِاللَّهِ وَلَوْ ءَامَنَ أَهْلُ الْكِتَابِ لَكَانَ خَيْرًا لَهُمْ مِنْهُمْ الْمُؤْمِنُونَ وَأَكْثَرُهُمُ الْفَاسِقُونَ ﴿١١٠﴾

You are the best of the nations raised up for (the benefit of) men; you enjoin what is right and forbid the wrong and believe in Allah; and if the followers of the Book had believed it would have been better for them; of them (some) are believers and most of them are transgressors. (Surah Ali Imran 3: 110)

Da'wah is not only obliged to *Ulama, Ustaz, fuqaha'*, or another Islamic expert, but da'wah is obliged for all Muslims around the world (Fariza Hanan, Kalthom, & Puziah, 2016), Therefore in conveying the message of da'wah, da'i need to see da'wah method or da'wah strategy (Zaid, 2017). Especially in this era of information technology where all of the peoples have depended on it, including multimedia that has changed many things in our lives (Saputra & Islamiyah, 2019).

We can listen to the music, view pictures, and watch videos from various platforms. However, for most modern society, the multimedia is more likely to be used for entertainment only. Some of them misuse it to do things that harm others. For a Muslim, when he sees something that is not good then as much as possible he needs to try to prevent or improve it in accordance with the level of ability (Al-Ghamidi,

2008).

Conveying the truth of Islamic teachings to mankind using the latest technology should be a priority for the preachers both individually and institutionally (Islamiyah, 2019). Every Muslim has an obligation to convey the truth of Islam with the language of his people, and today the language is described as information technology. And now we will conduct discussions about multimedia and of course, we will analyze the effectiveness of da'wah approach through multimedia among college students alumni located in the province of East Java.

Literature Review

Adam, Anuar, & Ali, (2014) said that the presence of digital-based information technology that has made online space especially blogs as the most productive place for religious preaching. They consider that blogs act as publishers of instant and accessible information. They run this study in Malaysia, and they found the fact that although blogs have been widely used as a tool for Islamic teachings, the use of this medium is still not fully accepted by some Muslim youths due to various factors.

In the next study Adam, Ali, Anuar, & Ali, (2015) in his research entitled "The New Media Challenge As The Medium of Religion Learning and Its Solution From The Perspective Of Islam" put forward some aspects of goodness in new internet-based media (whether through blogs, Facebook, twitter and so on) is done with the aim of spreading da'wah towards the user. Because the contribution of the internet as an essential vehicle

based on needs when to do da'wah and able to become powerful weapons of da'wah then the internet is seen relevant to the context of da'wah today. The similarity of this study because they discussed new media, but they did not analyze the effectiveness of da'wah through new media.

There is also a study about "The False Use of New Media and How to Handle It". In her paper, Nazim, (2015) explains that there are major issues that can be tied to the problem of using new media within the user circle that is from the aspect of the purpose of use and the validity of the information according to Islam. She found that there were two factors of new media problems among users; 1- The relationship of non-mahram male and female without supervision in the cyber. 2- Some information and news in the new media not using source validity technique. However, this study has not been discussed the effectiveness of da'wah through the new media (Che Daud & Abdullah, 2020).

Based on a study conducted by Ulinuha, (2009) in reviewing the da'wah strategy of the Nahdlatul Ulama (PBNU) through NU website (www.nu.or.id), found that some of the strategies implemented by PBNU provide any information needed by Muslims community and improve the service of religious information, such as Islamic law questioning. Interestingly, the website developed by the Board of Nahdlatul Ulama as the largest Islamic organization in the world (Alawi, 2013) also utilizes it as official page of NU organization.

However, this study is similar to previous research. He did not discuss the effectiveness of da'wah through the new media.

Based on the literature review above, there has been no discussion yet about the effectiveness of da'wah approach through multimedia among college students alumni of Ibrahimy University in East Java province, Indonesia. That's why multimedia and social media (Facebook) as part of new media will be the main focus of this study to see the effectiveness of da'wah approach. Hopefully, this study will contribute to the development of Islamic da'wah through the new media.

Methodology

1. Research Design

This research is a quantitative research that tests the effectiveness of da'wah approach through text, image, and video and through facebook platform as a mediator among college students alumni. The purpose of this research is to know the effectiveness of da'wah approach that college students alumni are interested in. The population of this research is college students alumni of Ibrahimy University who uses social media. Respondents of this research amounted to 100 people as samples taken from particular social media group from college students alumni of Ibrahimy University. Questionnaires are used as data collection methods. We made questionnaires with Google form apps. Data analysis method used is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) using IBM SPSS Amos software.

2. Research Framework

Figure 1. Research structural model using IBM SPSS Amos software

Result and Discussion

We need to implement a proven strategy to achieve da'wah through multimedia successfully, a proven strategy must be an essential point for da'wah practitioners. Da'wah strategy through multimedia needs an accurate identification to the reality of modern society, so that the strategies implemented are not out of dated, rigid and adaptable to the needs of the times (Saputra, Nazim, & Islamiyah, 2017). However, the principles of da'wah according to the Qur'an and Hadith are also implemented. For example; preach wisely, give good advice, and speak in a better way (Saputra & Islamiyah, 2019).

Based on this study, the Facebook construct was acted as mediator construct that is play a duo role which is become exogenous and endogenous constructs at the same time. Every exogenous construct that is video, picture and text had a link on Facebook and Da'wah construct.

Figure 2. Output of Structural Equation Models (SEM)

Based on the results above, video, picture, and text constructs had a significant effect on Facebook construct. Among exogenous constructs, the video and Facebook construct had a significant effect on Da'wah approach. In addition, it could see that the video construct is the most important construct that could produce a great impact on da'wah approach. In order to assess the mediating effect, the Baron & Kenny or Step-Wise approach is utilized (Baron & Kenny, 1986).

Table 1. Result of this study

		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Result
Facebook	<-- Video	.351	.072	4.890	***	Significant
Facebook	<-- Picture	.881	.262	3.360	***	Significant
Facebook	<-- Text	.578	.237	2.440	.015	Significant
Dakwah_Approach	<-- Video	.441	.077	5.705	***	Significant
Dakwah_Approach	<-- Face_Book	.292	.102	2.866	.004	Significant
Dakwah_Approach	<-- Picture	.118	.219	.540	.589	NotSignificant
Dakwah_Approach	<-- Text	.060	.194	.310	.757	Not Significant

To follow the Baron & Kenny guidelines, the indirect effect should be significant at first before determining the mediation result. The mediation is said exist when the indirect effect is greater than the direct effect (Chmura Kraemer, Kiernan, Essex, & Kupfer, 2008). The research hypotheses result for mediation analyses as follows:

Figure 3. Video – Facebook & Da'wah approach

Figure 3: The mediation construct do not occurred due to the small effect ($0.53 \times 0.28 = 0.1484 < 0.64$). Therefore, the facebook construct does not mediate the relationships between Video and Dakwah approach.

Figure 4. Picture – Facebook & Da’wah approach

Figure 4: The mediation construct occurred ($0.48 \times 0.28 = 0.1248 > 0.06$). Therefore, the facebook construct mediates the relationships between Picture and Dakwah approach

Figure 5. Text - Facebook & Da’wah approach

Figure 5: The mediation construct occurred ($0.33 \times 0.28 = 0.0924 > 0.03$). Therefore, the facebook construct mediates the relationships between Text and Dakwah approach.

Conclusion

Every Muslims have to do da'wah. This study proves that multimedia da'wah contents (video, pictures, and text) had a significant effect and positive impact through social media (Facebook). It's mean college students alumni prefer to enjoy multimedia da'wah contents through Facebook platform rather than another conventional platform. This study also proves that video and Facebook had a significant effect on Da'wah approach. But, the video is the most important thing that could produce a great impact on Da'wah approach although without using Facebook platform. However, pictures (photos, graphic or infographic) and text had a significant effect on da'wah approach by using Facebook platform.

Multimedia and social media (Facebook) have changed many things in our lives. We need to use it for da'wah approach because today everyone cannot ignore it. If more Moslems know how to do da'wah through multimedia, we can produce and double the positive impact of Islamic contents on the cyberspace, especially on social media (Facebook). Despite offering so many facilities, multimedia can be very dangerous for college students in the booming of social media. That's why, if this domain can not manage by a da'wah practitioner, the younger generation of Islam in the future will be further away from religion.

Limitation

This study had a limitation; we only use 100 respondents and they can fill out the form online directly through Google form apps. The respondents are college students alumni of Ibrahimy University located in the province of East Java, Indonesia who uses social media. Social media that we use as a mediator just Facebook only. However, the results of this study may have similar results in different places but with similar situation and conditions.

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